

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, Alison K. Post, and R. Chelsea Nagy

Orange Lava, Blue Lagoon
[NASA/Michala Garrison](#)

Quick Updates

- ESIL Director, Jennifer Balch, published a commentary in Nature: "[Extreme fire seasons are looming — science can help us adapt](#)".
- Earth Lab Interim Director, Virginia Iglesias, received a grant from the [CO-WY Engine](#) to study the built environment's susceptibility to wildfires.
- Virginia Iglesias was also featured in the news: [In a Parched US, Human-Triggered Wildfires Are Poised to Thrive](#).
- Alison Post, Earth Lab Program Manager, created a lesson on how to access data and images from the [PhenoCam Network](#). View the [tutorial here](#).
- The 2024-2025 cohort of the [Earth Data Analytics Professional Graduate Certificate](#) began in September with 19 students.
- Earth Lab was featured in an article from CU Boulder's Research and Innovation office. Read about our origins from CU Boulder's Grand Challenge initiative [here](#).
- Analytics Hub Director, Cibele Amaral published an article in the Journal of Applied Ecology: [Remote sensing approaches to monitor tropical forest restoration: Current methods and future possibilities](#)

New Science Paper: Fast Fires

We're proud to share that Jennifer Balch and several other Earth Lab researchers recently published an article in Science - and the article was featured on the cover!

The article, titled "[The fastest-growing and most destructive fires in the US \(2001 to 2020\)](#)," presents recent findings that the growth rate (speed) of wildfires across the US has increased substantially over the past two decades. It concluded that the "most destructive and deadly wildfires in US history were also fast."

Learn more about the study in [this article](#) by CIRES (Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences) at CU Boulder. The research was also featured in almost 20 different news outlets, including [The New York Times](#), [The LA Times](#), and [PBS \(video\)](#). Additionally, the research team developed a related [curriculum tool](#) in collaboration with the Center for Education, Engagement, and Evaluation ([CEEE](#)).

Additional Earth Lab authors include Virginia Iglesias, Adam Mahood, Max Cook, Cibele Amaral, Tyler McIntosh, Chelsea Nagy, Lise St. Denis, Ty Tuff, and Erick Verleye.

AGU24

In December, eight Earth Lab and ESIIIL team members presented their research at the American Geophysical Union (AGU) Annual Meeting in Washington, D.C. See a full list of Earth Lab/ESIIIL speakers and their presentation titles [here](#). Additional information (and links to abstracts) can be found in the CIRES AGU Highlights story [here](#).

Photos from @CIRESNEWS Instagram stories

[View our Schedule](#)
esiiil.org/agu24

AGU24
Washington, D.C. | 9-13 December 2024

The Chicago Symposium Series

On Friday, November 8, the Earth Lab/ESIIIL Education Team led a dynamic data science training workshop as part of the "[The Chicago Symposium Series on Excellence in Mathematics and Science: Research and Practice](#)," held at the Chicago Botanic Garden. The event featured a series of interactive sessions designed to build capacity in Environmental Data Science (EDS). Participants analyzed open weather and climate data from NOAA/NCEI, using the summer 2024 Chicago heatwave and the influence of Lake Michigan on local heat islands as a case study. Additional workshops focused on teaching coding skills for non-experts and managing cross-cultural student projects, emphasizing accessibility and collaboration in EDS. Explore the interactive curriculum [here](#).

Keynotes by Jim Sanovia (ESIIIL) and Elisha Yellow Thunder (South Dakota State University) offered insights into their personal journeys as enrolled Tribal members into EDS, highlighting pathways for increasing diversity in the field. Workshops were led by Nate Quarderer (Earth Lab/ESIIIL Education Director) and Elsa Culler (Earth Lab/ESIIIL Instructor and Curriculum Developer), who provided hands-on guidance to attendees. The event exemplified the missions of Earth Lab and ESIIIL to foster inclusive, innovative approaches to teaching and learning in EDS.

This event was made possible through the generous support of the Chicago Symposium team and by Dr. Alicia Foxx from the Chicago Botanic Garden. We were honored to offer this event to promote inclusion through an ethical blending of cultural knowledge, science, and technology.

EDS Seminar

We're kicking off the spring session of our Environmental Data Science (EDS) seminar series! We're looking for speakers- please email [Casey Jenson](#) if you are interested in speaking. Visit our [website](#) for information about how to join the email list and attend the seminars

ESIIIL Innovation Summit

[ESIIIL](#) is hosting its 3rd annual Innovation Summit: Environmental Tipping Points and Transformations in Boulder, Colorado from **May 28-30, 2025!** Visit the [summit website](#) to learn more and apply by **January 31st**.

[Apply Now](#)